

An Effective Heuristic Procedure For The Strong Double Tracing Problem

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Abstract: Given a non-directed connected graph G , which can be considered an especial kind of a connection system, there is an old Graph Theory problem consisting in finding, if it exists, a strong double tracing, that is, a tour traversing each edge of G exactly two non-consecutive times, one in each direction. This problem has been recently solved from a theoretical point of view, but there is not available any effective algorithm to this end. We present here a quick heuristic procedure to find a strong double tracing that can be easily programmed and that has been ran successfully in an exhaustive computational experience with 164 randomly generated examples. Finally, as application of the strong double tracing problem, we use our heuristic in order to solve a snow plowing problem in an area of Valencia (Spain).

Keywords: U-turn, strong double tracing, spanning tree.

1. INTRODUCTION

Graph Theory plays an essential part in the resolution of many optimization problems present in the real life, especially those involving vehicle routes: household refuse collection, snow plowing, school buses, inspection of oil or gas pipelines, pick up or delivery routes, and so on. For example, a city can be modelled to a graph in which vertices represent street intersections and arcs or edges represent one way or two ways (respectively) street segments between two intersections; if we assign to every arc or edge a cost equal to the length of the street segment it represents, many routing problems can be solved by finding, for instance, a minimum cost perfect matching, a minimum cost flow and/or a minimum cost spanning tree in the resultant graph. In the survey of Assad and Golden (1995) we can find a lot of information on this topic.

Graph Theory also provides an important tool for the Systems Theory. For example, we may describe the structure of some systems by means of a graph because there exists a kind of equivalence between many concepts defined on a graph and many concepts defined on a system. In fact, through Caselles (1992), we may consider a directed graph without costs assigned to its arcs as a particular type of system called connection system. Following Caselles, given a system with set of variables $V=\{v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n\}$ we may consider a directed graph $G=(V,A)$ where V is its set of vertices, A is its set of arcs and arc (u,v) belongs to A iff a change in variable u has a directed influence on the value of variable v . An input variable in the system is identified then with a vertex in G without entering arcs; a strict output variable with a vertex without leaving arcs; an isolated variable with an isolated vertex; a depending subsystem formed by the set of variables $U \subset V$ with the subgraph generated by the set of vertices U ; to check if a variable u has an indirect influence on the variable v , it is enough to see if it exists in G a directed path between u and v , and so on.

In addition to the Graph Theory elements already used in Systems Theory, we are convinced that many other problems involving graphs can help to the development of the System Theory, in the same way that purely theoretical problems about graphs have been

used years later to solve real life optimization problems, as it occurs with the problem that we study in this paper, called the *strong double tracing problem*. This problem was first raised by Ore (1951) from a theoretical point of view and 33 years later, Lemieux and Campagna (1984) study a snow plowing problem where it has a directed application, as we will see later.

The strong double tracing problem can be studied by using a directed graph (connection system) but we will work in a non-directed graph, as it has been studied in the Graph Theory literature. It can be defined in the following way: "Given a (non-directed) graph $G=(V,E)$, find a tour traversing each edge of G exactly two non-consecutive times, one in each direction or decide that no such tour exists". This problem can be solved in polynomial time; Benavent and Soler (1998) present a polynomial algorithm to find a strong double tracing (s.d.t.), but as they say, this algorithm is more theoretical than practical, because of two reasons: its complexity ($O(|E|^6)$) and its implementation difficulty (it uses some strong results on Graph Theory and Matroids Theory). In fact, Benavent and Soler do not implement their algorithm.

As we have said before, Lemieux and Campagna (1984) study a snow plowing problem where each street segment must be plowed on both sides. The travel graph is directed and Eulerian because it results from decomposing each street segment into two arcs of opposite directions. The main objective is then, trying to find an Eulerian tour that avoids the undesirable U-turns, that is, a s.d.t. in the original street network.

Recently, Soler (1998) studies a problem that generalizes the s.d.t. problem and that consists in finding an Eulerian tour without U-turns in a simple directed graph. This problem is obviously more useful in vehicle routing problems than the s.d.t. problem and in order to solve it, Soler's paper uses as essential subroutine, the s.d.t. problem. We find in these three last mentioned papers a justification of the work we show here.

We present in this paper an effective heuristic procedure to find a s.d.t. with a low complexity ($O(|V|^2|E|)$) and a very easy implementation. Despite our efforts, we have not proved that this algorithm works well in the general case. This is the reason why we say that it is a heuristic algorithm, but it ran successfully in an exhaustive computational experience with 164 randomly generated graphs with up to 166 vertices and 249 edges, all of them having a s.d.t., and that we think they represent the worst cases to find a s.d.t.. In Section 6 we use this heuristic in order to solve a snow plowing problem along the network of B-roads in a zone of La Plana d'Utiel, an area in the province of Valencia (Spain). We find in this network, a snow plowing route traversing both ways of the B-roads without making U-turns in the crossings of these roads, excepts for crossings inside a village, in which U-turns are allowed.

2. BASIC DEFINITIONS, NOTATIONS AND PREVIOUS RESULTS

Given a (non-directed) graph $G=(V,E)$ with V its set of vertices and E its set of arcs, $\{u_1, u_2, \dots, u_k\}$ is a **path** in G if $u_i \in V \forall i$, $u_i \neq u_j$ if $i \neq j$ and $(u_i, u_{i+1}) \in E \forall i=1, \dots, k-1$. If $u_1 = u_k$ we say that this path is a **cycle** and if $u_i = u_j$ for at least one $i \neq j$, we use the word **chain** (or **closed chain**) instead of path (or cycle). G is **connected** if there is a path between every pair of vertices in G ; in the opposite case we say that G is **disconnected**. A **connected component** of G is a maximal connected subgraph of G . A **cut vertex** in G is a vertex such that if we remove it from G , the number of connected components in G increases. A **block** in G is a maximal connected, **non-trivial** (= with more than one vertex) and without cut vertices subgraph of G . A **spanning tree** in G is a connected subgraph of G without cycles and containing all the vertices of G . Note that every spanning tree in G has $|V|-1$ edges. G is **Hamiltonian** if it contains a **Hamiltonian cycle** (= a cycle containing every vertex of G). E_v will denote the set of edges incident with vertex v , $d(v)$ will denote the **degree** of vertex v (=

the number of edges incident with v) and $d(G)$ will denote the minimum degree of its vertices. A vertex is called an **end-vertex** if it has degree 1. A **loop** is an edge (u,u) , $u \in V$. G is **cubic** if all its vertices have degree 3. Given a subgraph H of G , $V(H)$ will denote its set of vertices while $E(H)$ will denote its set of edges.

A **bidirectional double tracing** in G is a closed chain in G covering every edge of G exactly twice, one in each direction and a **strong double tracing** (s.d.t.) is a bidirectional double tracing such that no edge is traversed the second time immediately after being traversed the first time.

The problem of finding a s.d.t. was first raised by Ore (1951) and the first theoretical result related to this problem was given by Troy (1966):

Theorem 1: *Given $G=(V,E)$ such that $d(G) \leq 3$, if $|\{v \in V \mid d(v)=3\}| \equiv 0 \pmod{4}$, G does not have a strong double tracing.*

But it was Thomassen (1990) who gave the main result in order to solve Ore's problem:

Theorem 2: *A connected graph G has a s.d.t. if and only if G has no end-vertices and has a spanning tree T such that each connected component of $G-E(T)$ either has an even number of edges or contains a vertex which in G has degree at least 4.*

The importance of this result is based on the fact that there is a polynomial algorithm based on the *matroid parity problem* which either finds a tree as stated in Theorem 2 or decides that no such tree exists. A non totally correct proof of the existence of this polynomial algorithm was given by Thomassen and it was based on a paper of Gabow and Stallman (1986). Recently, Benavent and Soler (1998) give a counterexample to the proof given by Thomassen, a correct proof, and they describe a polynomial algorithm to construct, if it exists, a s.d.t. in G . Basically, this algorithm starts finding the tree T of Theorem 2 and then, applying a procedure called COVER, which first finds a bidirectional double tracing in T that only makes U-turns in its end-vertices and then, it successively enlarges this bidirectional double tracing to cover more and more edges, until a s.d.t. in G is obtained.

Finding the tree T of Theorem 2 or decide that no such tree exists by using the procedure described by Benavent and Soler, has complexity $O(|E|^6)$, while procedure COVER has complexity $O(|E|^2)$, then the whole procedure to find a s.d.t. has complexity $O(|E|^6)$.

From a theoretical point of view, the s.d.t. problem is then, an easy (polynomial) solvable problem. But taking into account that $|E|$ is greater or equal than $|V|$ in a connected graph without end-vertices, that in the worst case, for **simple graphs** (= graphs without more than one edge connecting the same pair of nodes and without loops) $|E|=|V|(|V-1|/2)$, and that in the Operational Research literature, a polynomial algorithm with polynomial degree in $|V|$ greater than 4 or 5 may be considered a non efficient algorithm, we have that the algorithm presented by Benavent and Soler is not a good procedure from a practical point of view. In fact, they have not implemented the algorithm; their work is strictly theoretic and in addition to the high polynomial degree, we have to take into account the complexity of the Gabow and Stalman's (1986) algorithm, used as a subroutine.

As the complexity of procedure COVER is $O(|E|^2)$, in order to have an effective procedure to construct a s.d.t. in a graph, we only have to determine a better way to find the tree of Theorem 2. That is what we try to do in the next two sections.

3. OTHER RESULTS ABOUT STRONG DOUBLE TRACINGS

Given a connected graph $G=(V,E)$, if G has a s.d.t., it is evident that it has no end-vertices. Moreover, we may suppose that G has no vertices of degree 2; for if $d(v)=2$, we can eliminate vertex v and add an edge joining the vertices adjacent to v , then the resultant graph has a s.d.t. iff G does.

We also may suppose that G has not more than one edge connecting the same pair of vertices. In the other case, we can replace one of the edges by the structure showed in Figure 1. Just by checking the 16 possible combinations, it is easy to see that G has a s.d.t. iff the new graph (with the structure of Figure 1) does.

Figure 1.
Substitution of a parallel edge for a "special" structure.

We may suppose too that

G has not any loop; for if G has a loop in a vertex with degree 3, it is easy to see that G does not admit a s.d.t. while if the loop occurs in a vertex with degree greater than 3, we may replace the loop with the structure of Figure 1.

Finally, we may suppose that G has not any cut vertex with degree 3 because of the following theorem:

Theorem 3: *Let $G=(V,E)$ be a connected graph with $d(G)>2$, without loops and with all its cut vertices with degree 3. Then G admits a s.d.t. if and only if every block in G with more than one edge admits a s.d.t.*

Proof:

Let us suppose that G admits a s.d.t.. Let B be a block in G with more than one edge and let v be a cut vertex, $v \in B$. Let D be a s.d.t. in G ; if $(u,v), (w,v) \in B$ and $(s,v) \notin B$, without loss of generality we may suppose that D makes in v turns $\{(u,v,w), (w,v,s), (s,v,u)\}$ because it does not make U-turns in v . If we change turns $\{(w,v,s), (s,v,u)\}$ for turn $\{(w,v,u)\}$ and we do this for every $v \in B$ cut vertex of G , we obtain a s.d.t. in B .

If every block in G with more than one edge admits a s.d.t., let us see that we can join these s.d.t. and the cycles (u,v,u) associated to every block with only one edge (u,v) , into a s.d.t. in G . These joinings occur necessarily at the cut vertices v of G , and we distinguish two cases:

- a) v belongs to three blocks in G , $\{(u,v)\}, \{(w,v)\}$ and $\{(s,v)\}$. Making turns $\{(u,v,w), (w,v,s), (s,v,u)\}$, no U-turns occur at vertex v .
- b) v belongs to two blocks B_1 and B_2 in G . We suppose without loss of generality that $(u,v), (w,v) \in B_1$ and that $B_2 = \{(s,v)\}$. The s.d.t. in B_1 necessarily makes turns $\{(u,v,w), (w,v,u)\}$. Making turns $\{(u,v,s), (s,v,w), (w,v,u)\}$ no U-turns occur at vertex v . \square

Note that, as consequence of Theorems 1 and 3, we have the following corollary:

Corollary 4: *Given a connected cubic graph G without loops, if it contains at least a block with more than one edge and with a number of vertices of degree three multiple of 4, then G does not admit a s.d.t.*

Taking into account all the suppositions made before, we will work in what follows with a *connected, simple, without end-vertices, without vertices of degree 2 and without cut vertices with degree 3 graph*, that will be denoted by G^* .

Definition 5: *Given a graph G^* and let H be a subgraph of G^* , we say that a connected component of $G-E(H)$ **complies with condition drf** (with regard to H) if it contains a vertex of degree at least 4 in G^* or if its number of edges has the same parity (even or odd) that its number of vertices not in H .*

Definition 6: *Given a graph G^* , we say that a connected subgraph H of G^* without cycles **complies with condition drf** if every connected component of $G-E(H)$ complies with condition drf.*

Theorem 7: *Let $G^*=(V,E)$ be a graph admitting a s.d.t. and with $|V|=n$. There exists a succession $H_1 \subset H_2 \subset \dots \subset H_{n-1}$ such that H_i is a connected subgraph of G^* without cycles that complies with condition drf and with $|E(H_i)|=i$ for all $i=1, \dots, n-1$.*

Proof:

By Theorem 2, there is a spanning tree T in G that complies with condition drf because each connected component of $G-E(T)$ with only vertices with degree 3 in G , has an even number of edges and its number of vertices not in T is 0.

Given $H_{n-1}=T$, let v be a vertex with degree 1 in H_{n-1} (note that v exists because H_{n-1} is connected and without cycles) and let (u,v) be the edge of H_{n-1} . If $d(u) \geq 4$ or $d(v) \geq 4$, it is evident that $H_{n-2}=H_{n-1}-\{(u,v)\}-\{v\}$ complies with condition drf while if $d(u)=d(v)=3$, as the connected components containing vertices u and v in $G-E(H_{n-1})$ comply with condition drf (it could be that both components be the same or that one of them be the empty set), if we remove edge (u,v) , the connected component of $G-E(H_{n-2})$ containing u and v has one more edge $((u,v))$ and one more vertex not in H_{n-2} (v), thus, if it not contains vertices with degree greater than 3 in G^* , its number of edges and its number of vertices not in H_{n-2} have the same parity, then H_{n-2} complies with condition drf and $|E(H_{n-2})|=n-2$.

If we carry on with H_{n-2} in the same way as we did with H_{n-1} , we obtain $H_{n-3}=H_{n-2}-\{(s,r)\}-\{s\}$ being s a vertex with degree 1 in H_{n-2} , such that H_{n-3} complies with condition drf and $|E(H_{n-3})|=n-3$. And so on, till H_1 is reached. \square

Therefore, a graph $G^*=(V,E)$ with $|V|=n$ admits a s.d.t. iff there exists a succession $H_1 \subset H_2 \subset \dots \subset H_{n-1}$ such that H_i is a connected subgraph of G^* without cycles that complies with condition drf and with $|E(H_i)|=i$ for all $i=1, \dots, n-1$. If we find an easy procedure to construct succession $H_1 \subset H_2 \subset \dots \subset H_{n-1}$ or to decide that no such succession exists and then, we apply procedure COVER to H_{n-1} , we will have an effective way to solve the s.d.t. problem in graph G^* .

4. ALGORITHM SDT-TREE

If the graph $G^*=(V,E)$ does not contain vertices with degree 3, it is evident that every spanning tree in G^* complies with the conditions of Theorem 2, so it is enough to find a spanning tree in G^* by means of a classical algorithm to this end, with complexity non greater than $O(|E|)$. Therefore, we will suppose that G^* contains at least a vertex v_1 with degree 3.

We present here a procedure to construct the succession $H_1 \subset H_2 \subset \dots \subset H_{n-1}$. If this procedure reaches H_{n-1} , then G^* admits a s.d.t.. If, in the opposite case, it does not reach H_{n-1} , despite our efforts, we have not proved yet that in these case G^* does not admit a s.d.t.. But supported by the computational experience given in Section 5 and by a result and a conjecture given at the end of this section, we are sure that, supposing that the algorithm does not work well from a theoretical point of view (we have not found any counterexample yet), the probability that G^* admits a s.d.t. when the algorithm does not reach H_{n-1} is very low. Moreover, in this last case, that probability will be practically zero if we introduce a little modification in the algorithm, as we will explain at the end of section 5.

Let then $G^*=(V,E)$ be a graph with at least a vertex v_1 with degree 3. We consider the following sets:

- P = set of vertices with label 0 (vertices will be labelled in the algorithm).
- Q = set of vertices with label 1.
- R = set of vertices with label 2.
- T = set of edges in the succession $H_1 \subset H_2 \subset \dots \subset H_{n-1}$.
- E^* = an auxiliary set of edges.
- $E_{v_1} = \{(v_1, u_1), (v_1, u_2), (v_1, u_3)\}$ (let us remember that G^* is a simple graph).

ALGORITHM SDT-TREE

Step 1 (initiation):

$$R = \{v_1, u_1, u_2, u_3\}$$

$$Q = \{v \in V \mid (u, v) \in E \text{ for some } u \in \{u_1, u_2, u_3\}\} - \{v_1, u_1, u_2, u_3\}$$

$$P = V - (R \cup Q)$$

$$T = E_{v_1}$$

$$E^* = \emptyset$$

Go to Step 3.

Step 2:

$$\forall u \in P \text{ such that } (u, v) \in E, \text{ do } P = P - \{u\}, Q = Q \cup \{u\}$$

Step 3:

Select $(s, w) \in E - E^*$ such that $s \in R$ and $w \in Q$ (to fix an order in the execution of the algorithm, as we suppose that each vertex has an associated number - s and w are numbers-, we select (s, w) according first to the smaller value of s and then to the smaller value of w).

$$\text{Do } E^* = E^* \cup \{(s, w)\}, T = T \cup \{(s, w)\}$$

Check if the connected components of $G^* - E(T)$ containing s and w comply with condition drf (note that perhaps s and w belong to the same connected component of $G^* - E(T)$).

$$\text{- If they do, do } R = R \cup \{w\}, Q = Q - \{w\}$$

- If $R = V$, **STOP**. T is the searched tree and then, G^* admits a s.d.t.

- If $R \neq V$, do $E^* = \emptyset$, $v = w$ and go to Step 2.

- If some of the (two or one) connected components do not comply with condition drf, do $T = T - \{(s, w)\}$. If $\exists (s, w) \in E$ such that $s \in R$ and $w \in Q$, and

$(s,w) \notin E^*$, go to Step 3. In other case, **STOP**, the algorithm cannot find the tree (if it exists).□

The complexity of algorithm SDT-TREE is $O(|V|^2/|E|)$ because each time we steady an edge in T ($|V|-4$ passings trough Step 2 in the worst case) we have to check less than $2|E|$ times if a connected component complies with condition drf and this checking needs less than $3|V|/2$ operations: we have to cover the connected component, if it contains a vertex with degree greater than 3 in G^* we stop, in other case, it is easy to see that the number of edges in this component is not greater than $3|V|/2$. This algorithm is easy to implement by using classical procedures of Graph Theory and let us remember that the procedure given by Benavent and Soler to find the tree of Theorem 2 has complexity $O(|E|^6)$.

Figure 2 shows an example of the execution of algorithm SDT-TREE. The graph G^* is the well-known Petersen cubic graph. By seeing the different drawings in Figure 2, it is easy to follow the steps of the algorithm till the tree of Theorem 2 is reached in the last drawing (given by bold edges). Note that in all the steps, $G-E(T)$ has a unique connected component and that after the fifth step 3, the algorithm tries to add to the tree, edge $(5,10)$, but in this case, $G-E(T)$ has two connected components with an odd number of edges and an even (0) number of vertices not in T : $\{5,2\}$ and $\{6,7,8,9,10\}$. Therefore, it tries with another edge, $(6,10)$.

It is easy to see that given a connected graph, for every connected subgraph H without cycles, there is a spanning tree T_H in G containing H . The following conjecture says that if the graph admits a s.d.t., this result is true even if we add the condition that H and T_H comply with condition drf.

Conjecture 8: Let $G^*=(V,E)$ be a graph admitting a s.d.t. and with $|V|=n$. For every $k \in \{1,2,\dots,n-2\}$, if algorithm SDT-TREE has found a succession $H_1 \subset H_2 \subset \dots \subset H_k$ such that H_i is a connected subgraph of G^* without cycles that complies with condition drf and with $|E(H_i)|=i$ for all $i=1,\dots,k$, then there exists a spanning tree T^k in G^* that complies with the conditions of Theorem 2 and such that $H_k \subset T^k$.

If Conjecture 8 were true, then, from a theoretical point of view, the algorithm would work perfectly (if G^* admits a s.d.t. the algorithm reaches H_{n-1}) and this would suppose an important improvement in Graph Theory in order to find a s.d.t. Let us see this:

Theorem 9: If Conjecture 8 is true, then if a graph G^* admits a s.d.t., algorithm SDT-TREE constructs the succession $H_1 \subset H_2 \subset \dots \subset H_{n-1}$ given in Theorem 7.

Figure 2: An example of algorithm SDT-TREE execution over the Petersen graph. Bold lines are the edges of the tree constructed by the algorithm.

Proof:

We proceed by induction. SDT-TREE reaches H_3 in Step 1 ($H_1=\{(v_1, u_1)\}$, $H_2=\{(v_1, u_1), (v_1, u_2)\}$, $H_3=\{(v_1, u_1), (v_1, u_2), (v_1, u_3)\}$), because $G^* - \{(v_1, u_1), (v_1, u_2), (v_1, u_3)\} - \{v_1\}$ is connected (G^* has not any cut vertex with degree 3); then, if this unique connected component does not contain a vertex with degree greater than 3 in G^* , it means that G^* is a cubic graph. This implies that $|E|=3|V|/2$ and by Theorem 1 that $|V|\equiv 2 \pmod{4}$, then, $|E|$ is odd and $|E|-3$ is even. As $|V|-4$ is also even, we have that H_3 complies with condition drf.

Suppose that SDT-TREE has found $H_1 \subset H_2 \subset \dots \subset H_k$ such that H_i is a connected subgraph of G^* without cycles that complies with condition drf and with $|E(H_i)|=i$ for all $i=1, \dots, k$, $3 \leq k < n-1$, let us see that it can find H_{k+1} such that $H_k \subset H_{k+1}$ and H_{k+1} is a connected subgraph of G^* without cycles that complies with condition drf and with $|E(H_{k+1})|=k+1$.

If Conjecture 8 is true, there is a tree T' in G^* satisfying the conditions of Theorem 2 such that $H_k \subset T'$. Suppose $E(T')=E(H_k) \cup \{e_{k+1}, \dots, e_{n-1}\}$. There is at least one vertex v' in $G^* - H_k$ with degree 1 in T' ($d_{T'}(v')=1$), in other case we have that

$$2(n-1) = \sum_{T'} d_{T'}(v) \geq \sum_{H_k} d_{H_k}(v) + \sum_{T'-H_k} d_{T'}(v) + 1 \geq 2(k-1) + 2(n-k) + 1 = 2(n-1) + 1 \quad \text{due}$$

to the fact that T' has $n-1$ edges (and then, the sum of the degrees respect to T' of its vertices is $2(n-1)$), H_k has $k-1$ edges and there exists at least one edge in T' connecting H_k with the rest of T' . This is absurd.

Let then e_{n-1} be the only edge in T' incident to v' , then, $T''=T'-\{e_{n-1}\}-\{v'\}$ complies with condition drf and with $|E(T'')|=n-2$, the reasoning is identical to the one given in the proof of Theorem 7. If we carry on with T'' in the same way as we did with T' (T'' has a vertex not in H_k with degree 1 in T'' ...) and so on, we arrive to $T^{n-k-1}=H_k \cup \{e_{k+1}\}$ that complies with condition drf and with $|E(T^{n-k-1})|=k+1$. Therefore, it is enough to take $H_{k+1}=T^{n-k-1}$. \square

5. COMPUTATIONAL RESULTS

Despite our efforts, we have not proved Conjecture 8 and then, we have not been able to prove that algorithm SDT-TREE reaches H_{n-1} when G^* admits a s.d.t.. Therefore, to see its efficiency, we have implemented it in Pascal and tested it on a Pentium II 350. Firstly on a set of several cubic graphs, some of them non Hamiltonian (as the Petersen graph or the Tutte graph), and then, on a set of 164 randomly generated Hamiltonian cubic graphs with up to 166 vertices and (necessarily) 249 edges.

We have tried cubic graphs because these are the graphs in which the existence of a s.d.t. is less probable, due to the fact that, obviously, given a spanning tree T in G^* , none of the connected components of $G^* - E(T)$ has a vertex with degree greater than 3 in G^* . In fact, vertices with degree 3 in G^* are the only ones in which U-turns may appear in a bidirectional double tracing with minimum number of U-turns. This is due to the fact that if a bidirectional double tracing makes a U-turn in a vertex with degree greater than 3, it can be easily transformed into another bidirectional double tracing without U-turns in that vertex (see Theorem 2.4. of Benavent and Soler (1998)).

If we had randomly generated cubic graphs without initial restrictions, as G^* must be connected, simple and without cut vertices of degree three, we would have had to check later if the graphs comply with these conditions and probably we would have had to reject most of them. Therefore, we have generated Hamiltonian cubic graphs (if a graph is Hamiltonian, is

connected and without cut vertices) with a number of vertices $|V| \equiv 2 \pmod{4}$. If $|V| \equiv 0 \pmod{4}$ we know by Theorem 1 that G^* does not have a s.d.t.

The question is: as the procedure proposed by Benavent and Soler to find a s.d.t. is not implemented, if our algorithm does not reach H_{n-1} in one of these graphs, how can we know if the graph admits or does not admit a s.d.t.? Soler (1998) proved that a s.d.t. problem can be transformed into a Hamiltonian cycle problem in a directed graph, the trouble is that the Hamiltonian cycle problem is a **NP-Complete** problem (=its resolution takes an exponential time in the worst case) and it has no sense to solve a polynomial problem by transforming it into a NP-Complete problem in the general case. But this transformation can be a good tool in order to prove the efficiency of other procedures, as it occurs in our case, because we have available a code to solve the Hamiltonian cycle problem in a directed graph, due to Fischetti and Toth (1992).

We can only test s.d.t. problems in cubic graphs with up to 166 vertices because of the complexity of Fischetti and Toth's algorithm and of the computer memory it consumes. Therefore we have created 4 randomly Hamiltonian cubic graphs with $4n+2$ vertices, $n \in \{1, 2, \dots, 41\}$ (164 graphs in total), all of them having a s.d.t..

The results are totally satisfactory: in all of the 164 cubic graphs, our algorithm have reached H_{n-1} in less than one second. Our conclusion is that it will be very difficult to find an example in which our algorithm misses. Anyway, for if Conjecture 8 were not true, in order to increase the efficiency of the algorithm, we may execute it as many times as vertices of degree 3 exist in G^* , starting each time in one of those vertices. This implies a low increment of the complexity, $O(k|V|^2/|E|)$ where k is the number of vertices with degree three in G^* , whereas it will be practically impossible that this modified procedure does not reach H_{n-1} when G^* admits a s.d.t. because if, in a set of 164 random Hamiltonian cubic graphs, our algorithm has always found the tree starting from vertex 1, k executions of the algorithm (in the worst case), starting each one in a different vertex with degree 3, will increase the probability of success.

We have not present any table with computational results for several reasons: the algorithm does not provide any value that must be compared with another one (just only reaches or not H_{n-1} and it always did it), the CPU time consumed in all the examples was insignificant (less than one second) and the structure of the generated graphs is very clear. But of course, these graphs and the code of the algorithm are available to every one interested in this topic.

6. AN APPLICATION TO A SNOW PLOWING PROBLEM

As a practical application of the strong double tracing problem, we solve in this section the problem of finding a snow plowing route. This route consists in traversing both ways of a set of B-roads without making U-turns in the crossings, except for crossings inside a village, in which U-turns are allowed. The network of these B-roads corresponds to a zone of La Plana d'Utiel, which is an area of the province of Valencia (Spain) sometimes covered with snow in winter.

Figure 3 shows the map of this zone and Figure 4 shows the graph associated with the involved B-roads and villages. An edge corresponds with a road segment between two crossing or villages (represented by vertices). When a vertex is represented by a square, it means that this vertex has degree two or three and that it represents a village; U-turns are considered allowed in this vertex because the crossings occurs in a village. Note that this graph has three end-vertices so the tour solution will make at least three U-turns. In order to

use the heuristic, we have to transform this graph into another simple graph without end-vertices, without vertices of degree two and, in such a way that the tour solution could make U-turns in the square vertices.

To avoid end-vertices, we only have to remove these vertices and their incident edges from the graph. The removal of the three end-vertices in Figure 4 leads to the existence of three vertices of degree two. We also remove these vertices from the graph (in the way explained at the beginning of Section 3). This leads to the existence of two edges connecting the same pair of vertices (Venta del Moro and Casas de Prado). Therefore, we substitute one of these edges for the “special” structure given in Figure 1. Finally, in order to allow that the tour solution could make U-turns in the square vertices, it is easy to see that it is sufficient to add at each square vertex, the “special” structure given in Figure 1. After all these changes, we obtain the graph G^* given in Figure 5. In graph G^* we will apply heuristic STD-TREE and to this end, we have numbered all the vertices of G^* .

Algorithm SDT-TREE finds a spanning tree T such that each connected component of $G^* - E(T)$ either has an even number of edges or contains a vertex which in G^* has degree at least 4. Figure 6 shows this tree; its edges, in bold lines, are numbered according to the order in which the algorithm fix them. The reader can easily follow the construction of this tree by seeing Figure 5 and Figure 6, taking into account the number assigned to each vertex in G , and following the steps of heuristic SDT-TREE.

Once tree T is obtained, in order to find the strong double tracing in G^* from T , we manually apply procedure COVER, given by Benavent and Soler (1998). Finally, we transfer this strong double tracing to the original graph (Figure 4) and we obtain a snow plowing route consisting in traversing both ways of the B-roads without making U-turns in the crossings, except for crossings inside a village, in which U-turns are allowed. The snow plowing route is given in Figure 7, where each edge of the original graph has been replaced for two arcs of opposite directions. The arcs has been numbered according to the order in which they are traversed in the tour, starting in vertex 1.

Figure 3: Map of the zone of La Plana d'Utiel.

Figure 4: Graph associated with the involved roads and villages.

Figure 5. Graph G^* in which we have to solve the s.d.t. problem. Its vertices have been numbered in order to apply algorithm SDT-TREE.

Figure 6. The spanning tree T founded by algorithm SDT-TREE (its edges, in bold lines, are numbered according to the order in which the algorithm fix them). The graph admits then a s.d.t.

Figure 7: Strong double tracing solution transferred to the original graph (Figure 4). The tour only makes U-turns in the end-vertices and in some of the square vertices, in which U-turns are allowed.

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